

**Title: Are the Data True? A Post-Publication Integrity Assessment of a
Landmark IVF Randomized Controlled Trial**

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Abstract

Background

Given the central role of randomized controlled trials (RCTs) in evidence-based medicine, the assessment of their trustworthiness is essential. Despite growing recognition of untrustworthy trials in recent years, efforts to systematically identify problematic data and exclude such studies from evidence synthesis remain limited.

Objective

The current report aimed to apply The Checklist to Assess Trustworthiness in RAndomised Controlled Trials (TRACT) checklist to a highly cited NEJM RCT comparing frozen versus fresh embryo transfer in women without polycystic ovary syndrome (PCOS). The trial assessed in this report directly informs clinical guidelines and Cochrane systematic reviews on the freeze-all strategy in assisted reproduction.

Methods

The TRACT checklist (19 items across seven domains) was applied to the index trial (Vuong et al., NEJM 2018; NCT02471573) using the published paper, the conference abstract, and all archived versions of the clinical trial registry as primary data sources. P-values for baseline characteristics were independently recalculated using summary statistics.

Results

The assessment identified nine concerns, seven of which were rated as major spanning five of the seven domains. Specific concerns included: a chronological impossibility in the reported recruitment timeline; incomplete conflict of interest declarations across six of nine authors

violating COPE and ICMJE standards; a pattern of retractions within the same author group; simultaneous recruitment of overlapping trials at the same center; an implausible absence of participant attrition (0%); an internal contradiction within baseline characteristics comprising both implausibly perfect balance and statistically significant imbalances in causally linked variables that were not reported by the authors; unreported clinically important prognostic factors; and an accelerated recruitment rate representing a greater than 50% reduction in the planned recruitment duration without explanation.

Conclusions

The concerns raised in this analysis indicate that, irrespective of methodological rigor, citation impact, or the prestige of the publishing journal, the trustworthiness of an RCT may still be substantially compromised. These findings underscore the need for greater scrutiny and highlight the importance of incorporating structured integrity assessment tools to enhance transparency and ensure that clinical decisions and evidence synthesis are based on trustworthy data.

1. Introduction

Since the introduction of vitrification, the transfer of frozen embryos has become more feasible, leading to a shift in clinical practice toward cryopreservation of all embryos with deferred transfer in a subsequent frozen cycle, a strategy known as the ‘freeze-all’ approach. This strategy has been increasingly adopted in clinical practice due to its potential to improve endometrial receptivity, avoid the supraphysiological hormonal environment associated with stimulated cycles, and reduce the risk of ovarian hyperstimulation syndrome (OHSS). *The New England Journal of Medicine* (NEJM) published three randomized controlled trials (RCTs) between 2016 and 2018 that have been highly influential in shaping the evidence base on this topic. One of these RCTs reported improved live birth rates among women with polycystic ovary syndrome (PCOS) using a ‘freeze-all’ strategy.[1] However, the other two RCTs did not demonstrate a similar benefit in either ovulatory [2] or non-PCOS [3] women.

Given the clinical importance of these trials, the reliability of their findings is critical. However, increasing concerns have been raised about the trustworthiness of RCTs across medical disciplines [4]. It has been estimated that 44% of RCTs submitted to the journal *Anaesthesia* contained falsified data, while 26% were fabricated [5]. Cochrane reviews of ante- and postnatal nutritional interventions have recently incorporated integrity checks in their evidence synthesis, leading to the exclusion of 25% of included RCTs due to concerns regarding their trustworthiness [6]. The field of reproductive medicine is no exception; in recent years, there has been an increasing number of retractions involving problematic data [7]. Similarly, the International Evidence-Based Guideline for PCOS, which incorporated integrity assessment into its evidence synthesis, excluded 45% of RCTs for failing to meet required trustworthiness criteria

[8]. In response to these concerns, structured integrity assessment tools have been developed to enable systematic and transparent evaluation of RCT trustworthiness, such as the Checklist to Assess Trustworthiness in Randomised Controlled Trials (TRACT) [9]. Unlike traditional risk-of-bias tools, which assess methodological quality, the TRACT checklist addresses a different question—whether the reported data are internally consistent, plausible, and credible.

One of the major obstacles to addressing post-publication concerns in the literature is the limited correspondence window imposed by journals. Most journals policies nowadays follow the recommendations of the Committee on Publication Ethics (COPE) in addressing post-publication concerns, *however*, COPE's guidelines explicitly have no time limit in this regard. For example, NEJM allows only a three-week period after article publication for submission of letters to the editor, after which the opportunity to raise concerns is effectively closed. This timeframe is often insufficient to conduct a thorough and transparent assessment of RCT's trustworthiness. Integrity evaluations require detailed scrutiny of all related materials, including trial registry histories, conference abstracts, and study protocols. In addition, the underlying data may require reanalysis and verification of reported summary statistics. Post-publication platforms such as PubPeer provide an alternative avenue for raising concerns; *however*, they lack formal peer review, demonstrate low author response rates (approximately 7.5%), and offer limited capacity for systematic verification or replication of the issues raised [10]. In this context, the use of structured integrity assessment frameworks, such as the TRACT tool, represents a more transparent and reproducible approach to evaluating and raising concerns. Raising such concerns publicly using a transparent tool is beneficial, not only to detect problematic studies, but also to enrich the scientific community with information that accumulatively will help in the future to prevent any form of errors, either intentional or non-intentional, before publishing. It could also

be beneficial if the journals offer a separate, time-unlimited channel for structured integrity assessments.

In this report, one of the largest and most influential RCTs underpinning the use of the ‘freeze-all’ strategy in non-PCOS women was checked for trustworthiness using the TRACT checklist [3]. Multiple concerns were identified that affect the transparency, internal consistency, and overall trustworthiness of the trial.

2. Methods

2.1. TRACT checklist

This report represents a formal assessment of the trustworthiness of a randomized controlled trial (RCT) comparing freeze-all versus fresh embryo transfer in non-PCOS patients (trial registry: NCT02471573), published in the NEJM in 2018 [3].

The assessment was conducted using the TRACT tool. This checklist comprises 19 items across 7 domains. Each item is evaluated and rated as major concern, some concerns/no information, or no concern. Based on the overall pattern of findings, the trial is subsequently classified as having high, moderate, or low risk of integrity concerns.

All TRACT items were assessed by the author based on predefined criteria and documented evidence from the included sources. The assessment focused on the transparency of trial governance, the coherence of the study methodology, and the internal consistency of reported data, rather than the clinical effectiveness of the intervention.

2.2. Ethical statement

Since this report involved appraisal of previously published research, no ethical approval was required. This evaluation does not constitute an allegation of research misconduct. All information used in this assessment was obtained from publicly available sources, and the approach is consistent with guidance from the COPE on post-publication review.

2.3.Data sources

The assessment was based on multiple publicly available sources, including the primary publication in the NEJM [3], the American Society for Reproductive Medicine (ASRM) Annual Meeting 2016 abstract [11], and the clinical trial registry (NCT02471573).

The study protocol was not included in the assessment, as it was made available only as a supplementary file alongside the final publication and was not prospectively accessible. As such, it does not meet the transparency requirements for independent verification.

To identify prior retractions or expressions of concern related to the author group, searches were conducted in PubMed and the Retraction Watch database, in addition to reviewing individual author publication records.

2.4.Statistical verification

No access to individual participant data was available, and the assessment was therefore limited to reported summary data. P-values for selected baseline characteristics were independently recalculated from reported summary data using a two-sample *t*-test method [12] , as recommended by the TRACT checklist developers.

These calculations are based on summary statistics and are therefore approximate; however, they are sufficient to identify large discrepancies between reported and recalculated results.

3. Results

A comprehensive assessment was conducted using the TRACT checklist, which comprises 19 items across seven domains, with detailed address of all items, presented in Table 1. Of these, 11 items were rated as having no concerns, 2 items as having some concern/no information, and 7 items as having major concerns. Notably, major concerns were identified across five of the seven domains. Taken together, this pattern of findings classifies the current RCT in question [3] as being at high risk of integrity concerns. Identified concerns are summarized as follows:

3.1. Inconsistent end of recruitment timelines

Concern: The authors reported consistent recruitment dates in both the NEJM trial and the final version of trial registry (30 June 2015 to 10 April 2016). However, data from this RCT were presented as an abstract at the American Society for Reproductive Medicine (ASRM) 2016 conference [11]. The abstract presented consistent number of randomized participants and clinical outcomes up to ongoing pregnancies [11] with the published NEJM trial [3]. Considering the abstract submission deadline for the ASRM conference (April 2016), the fact that data cannot be modified after submission, and that to reach ongoing pregnancies it takes at least 12 weeks after ET, reported recruitment end date (April 2016) of the trial seems implausible.

This concern is further compounded by discrepancies in the trial registry. Versions 1 through 3 of NCT02471573 estimated primary completion in June 2017 — 14 months later than the date reported in the final registry version and the published manuscript. The retroactive revision of

the primary completion date, combined with the chronological impossibility identified above, raises fundamental questions about the reliability and internal consistency of the documented study timeline.

Trustworthiness implication: Consistent and transparent reporting of study timelines across all related publications is a core element of effective study governance. [13]. The inconsistency in recruitment timelines undermines the credibility of the reported study timeline and raises doubts about the transparency and reliability of trial governance.

TRACT rating: Major concern

3.2. Incomplete COI declaration

Concern: The authors stated that the trial was funded by My Duc Hospital, Ho Chi Minh City, Vietnam; *however*, the role of the funder in the conduct of the trial remains unclear. The funder is not a neutral external body; *however*, it is the same commercial enterprise that owns the hospital, employs the investigators and runs the site where patients were recruited. There is no structural separation between any of these roles.

Whilst the presence of an independent data and safety monitoring committee provides a degree of oversight in data monitoring, this does not mitigate the broader risks introduced by the funder's undisclosed structural role, which potentially extends to study design, participant selection, data collection, analysis, interpretation of findings, and the decision to publish.

Furthermore, six of the nine authors were employed by My Duc Hospital. The authors did not disclose any potential conflicts of interest related to the funder in their disclosure statements.

Trustworthiness implication: COPE and ICMJE guidance consider failure to disclose relevant relationships a serious breach of reporting standards.

TRACT rating: Major concern

3.3.Author group

Concern: Multiple retractions were identified involving studies from the same institution as the index RCT, with overlapping investigators. One RCT was retracted due to duplication [14]. Another RCT abstract was withdrawn at the authors' request because of substantial data errors and inconsistent conclusions [15]. Two studies were retracted upon author request without provided justification [16,17]. A secondary analysis related to the current RCT [3] also underwent a post-publication correction [18].

Trustworthiness implication: A pattern of retractions within the same author group constitutes a significant credibility concern, particularly when retractions are due to integrity issues or are unexplained. Additionally, the volume of RCTs produced by the lead investigator group from a single center exceeds the threshold identified in the TRACT framework as a credibility concern.

TRACT rating: Major concern

3.4.Recruitment process and competing trials

Concern: The CONSORT flow chart indicates that 294 screened patients (9.6% of the total screened population) were excluded from recruitment due to participation in other trials.

However, neither the published manuscript nor the protocol provides sufficient detail on how this was managed to ensure unbiased and consecutive patient enrollment. In addition, the NEJM trial

[3] was conducted during a period when three other RCTs were recruiting at the same center in [19–21]. Two of these trials appear to have enrolled patients who could also have been eligible for the current study[20,21].

Trustworthiness implication: The absence of detailed reporting on how competing trial recruitment was managed reduces confidence in the integrity of the enrollment process. This raises concerns about potential selection bias, which may affect the comparability of groups and the validity of the study findings.

TRACT rating: Major concern

3.5. Recruitment rate and feasibility

Concern: The study protocol indicated that trial completion was expected in June 2016; *however*, the study was reported as completed approximately 2.5 months earlier. As the protocol lacked sufficient transparency for detailed verification, it was not relied upon for assessment. Instead, clinical trial registry records (NCT02471573) were examined as a more transparent and trackable source. Registry versions 1 to 3 indicate that the primary completion date was initially estimated as June 2017, consistent with a planned recruitment period beginning in June 2015 (Table 2). In contrast, recruitment was reported as completed on 10 April 2016—more than one year earlier than planned, representing over 50% reduction in the anticipated recruitment duration.

Trustworthiness implication: The accelerated recruitment rate (approximately 2.4 times faster than initially planned) raises concerns about the reliability of the recruitment process and adherence to the planned methodology, particularly considering the large sample size enrolled

within a short period and the concurrent recruitment of participants into three other studies during the same timeframe.

TRACT rating: Major concern

3.6.Drop-out Rate

Concern: The authors anticipated a 10% loss to follow-up in their sample size calculation; *however*, the reported rate in the trial was 0%. The paper explicitly states that “follow-up data were complete for all women in the study”.

This level of completeness appears unusual in the context of the study design. The trial included a relatively large sample size and multiple follow-up time points, including cumulative outcomes assessed up to one year after randomization—factors that typically increase the likelihood of some attrition. In addition, within this clinical context, it is generally expected that some participants may not complete all stages of treatment or follow-up. For example, cycle cancellations (e.g., due to failed endometrial preparation or non-viable embryos), protocol deviations, or patient withdrawal due to emotional, physical, or financial burden are frequently encountered in clinical practice.

Trustworthiness implication: A complete absence of loss to follow-up—particularly when not explained—raises concerns regarding the plausibility of participant flow and data completeness.

TRACT rating: Major Concern

3.7. Baseline balance and plausibility

Concern: Independent re-calculation of P-values indicates that the number of two-pronuclear (2PN) fertilized oocytes (8 ± 4 vs 9 ± 4 ; $p = 0.0005$) and cleavage embryos (6 ± 3 vs 7 ± 3 ; $p < 0.0001$) differ statistically between groups, despite the authors reporting “no significant differences”.

Concurrently, multiple other baseline variables demonstrate a perfect and near perfect balance that is statistically extraordinary for a trial of this size: age and body mass index are reported as identical in both groups; oocyte retrieval and metaphase II counts are near-identical [9]. The coexistence of implausibly perfect balance across multiple variables and unreported, highly significant imbalances in causally derived downstream variables — which occupy intermediate positions in a biologically constrained sequential cascade (oocyte retrieval → MII oocytes → 2PN fertilization → cleavage → good day-3 embryos) — is internally contradictory and cannot be explained by the properties of any legitimate randomization process.

Trustworthiness implication: Failure to report statistically significant baseline differences raises concerns regarding selective reporting. Furthermore, internally inconsistent or difficult-to-explain data patterns warrant scrutiny, particularly when they relate to the plausibility of the randomization process.

TRACT rating: Major concern

3.8. Unreported important prognostic factors

Concern: Two clinically important prognostic factors were not reported in the primary publication and could materially influence the observed outcomes. First, the quality of embryos

transferred was not described at the level of the actual embryo transfer. Although the authors reported overall grade A embryos per stimulated cycle, this does not ensure that the quality of embryos ultimately transferred was comparable between groups at the time of ET. Given that embryo selection is a key determinant of success in assisted reproduction, imbalance at this level could confound the results [22].

Second, endometrial thickness—an important predictor of implantation and live birth—was not reported in the main trial publication. Notably, this variable was analyzed in a subsequent subgroup or secondary analysis of the same RCT [18], indicating that the data were available but not included in the primary report [3].

Trustworthiness implication: The omission of these prognostic factors limits the ability to assess comparability between groups and raises concerns about the robustness of the reported outcomes. Selective non-reporting of clinically relevant variables—especially when they are measured and later analyzed—may introduce bias in interpretation and is compatible with selective reporting practices. These omissions reduce transparency and hinder independent evaluation of whether the observed treatment effect reflects a true intervention effect or residual confounding.

TRACT rating: Some concern

3.9. Time from study completion to submission

Concern: The submission date for this *NEJM* is not publicly available, limiting direct assessment of the interval between study completion and manuscript submission. However, data

up to ongoing pregnancies were publicly presented at ASRM conference (April 2016) before they could logically have been collected under the reported timeline.

Trustworthiness implication: The absence of a reported submission date, combined with the apparent mismatch between the trial timeline and the timing of publicly presented results, reduces confidence in the transparency and internal consistency of study reporting. This may raise concerns regarding the completeness or timing of outcome data collection.

TRACT rating: no information

Discussion

The current RCT under assessment recruited a large sample of patients and applied a rigorous methodology to address whether a ‘freeze-all’ strategy is more beneficial than fresh embryo transfer in non-PCOS patients. Its publication in a high-impact journal led clinicians and the wider scientific community to place considerable trust in its findings. However, application of the TRACT tool identified nine concerns, seven of which were rated as major, relating to inadequacies in trial governance, incomplete conflict of interest declarations, inconsistencies in timelines and data reporting, potential improper randomization, and compromised internal consistency of the reported data.

The current RCT has been widely cited in clinical guidelines, extending its influence beyond the original findings. Its results have now been incorporated into the Cochrane Review [23] and numerous other meta-analyses, thereby contributing significantly to the evidence base that shapes current clinical practice. Engagement of the scientific community in this discussion is not merely timely — it is essential. The concerns documented here serve a dual purpose. First, they

demand a transparent and detailed response from the authors to ensure that the reported findings are sufficiently trustworthy to inform clinical decisions affecting patient safety. Second, these concerns are intended to stimulate broader scientific debate about the responsibility of researchers, institutions, journals, and guideline bodies to evaluate RCT integrity throughout the entire lifecycle of a trial — from conception and registration, through conduct and analysis, to publication and evidence synthesis. In an era in which individual trials can directly shape clinical guidelines and influence the care of thousands of patients, the systematic and transparent assessment of research trustworthiness is not an optional scholarly exercise, but a professional and ethical obligation shared by the entire reproductive medicine community [24].

This report has some strengths. First, the concerns raised were not based on opinion; rather, they were identified using the TRACT tool, a transparent and systematic approach. The effectiveness of the TRACT tool in detecting problematic RCTs has been demonstrated in several cases involving publication integrity [7]. Second, the assessment considered all the presentations and documents of the RCT in question and extended to other external sources such as authors retractions and competing RCTs in the same facility.

One limitation of this report is that the assessment of this trial using TRACT checklist was not done in independence. However, the clarity of methodology, the adherence to the recommendations provided by the developers and the detailed reporting of the concerns raised make the process of assessment transparent and reproducible. Furthermore, the assessment is based on publicly available information, and access to raw data and full trial audits were not available. As such, the findings should be interpreted as signals of concern rather than definitive evidence of misconduct.

In conclusion, the convergence of multiple independent concerns raises substantial uncertainty regarding the internal consistency and transparency of the trial. While none of these issues alone is definitive, their combined presence warrants cautious interpretation of the findings and highlights the need for independent verification. More broadly, they reinforce the importance of integrating structured trustworthiness assessments into the evaluation of clinical trials to ensure that healthcare decisions are based on reliable and credible evidence.

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YM: Conceptualization, Investigation, Writing– original draft, Writing– review & editing.

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Generative AI statement

In preparing this manuscript, the author used artificial intelligence (AI) tools to enhance the clarity of writing and check spelling and grammar. Prior to submission, the author reviewed the content edited by AI and took full responsibility for the content of the submitted manuscript.

Conflict of interest

The author declared that this work was conducted in the absence of any personal, commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

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